

Controlling the flow balance: In vitro characterization of a pulsatile total artificial heart in preload and afterload sensitivity

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to identify the preload and afterload sensitivity of the ReinHeart TAH 2.0. For adequate left-right flow balance, the concept of a reduced right stroke volume (by about 10%) and active adaption of the right diastole duration are evaluated concerning the controllability of the flow balance. This study used an active mock circulation loop to test a wide range of preload and afterload conditions. Preload sensitivity was tested at atrial pressures (APs) between 4 and 20 mm Hg. Left afterload was varied in a range of 60–140 mm Hg mean aortic pressure (MAP), right afterload was simulated between 15 and 40 mm Hg. Four scenarios were developed to verify that the flow difference fully covers the defined target range of 0–1.5 L/min. Although a positive correlation between inlet pressure and flow is identified for the right pump chamber, the left pump chamber already fills completely at an inlet pressure of 8–10 mm Hg. With increasing afterload, both the left and right flow decrease. A positive flow balance (left flow exceeds right flow) is achieved over the full range of tested afterloads. At high APs, the flow difference is limited to a maximum of 0.7 L/min. The controllability of flow balance was successfully evaluated in four scenarios, revealing that a positive flow difference can be achieved over the full range of MAPs. Under physiological test conditions, the linear relationship between flow and heart rate was confirmed, ensuring good controllability of the TAH.

KEYWORDS

in vitro study, mechanical circulatory support, mock circulation loop, physiological control, pulsatile blood pump, total artificial heart

1 | INTRODUCTION

A total artificial heart (TAH) as bridge or alternative therapy to transplantation is an emerging option for the treatment of irreversible biventricular heart failure, partly inevitable due to the mismatch between organ donations and demand.^{1,2} For several decades, the research on an artificial heart

replacement has been carried out at the Helmholtz Institute in Aachen.^{3–5} The development of a patented linear actuator formed the basis for the TAH ReinHeart.^{6–8} The TAH replaces the function of the natural heart and is implanted as an orthotopic heart replacement with complete excision of both ventricles. Several studies have demonstrated the proof of concept, as well as initial results in terms of durability,⁹

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hemocompatibility,¹⁰ implantable driver electronics,^{11,12} and preliminary in vivo performance.¹³ In numerical simulations, a fluid–structure interaction model was developed, and the pump chamber was analyzed with regard to the chamber washout behavior and inlet valve orientation.^{14,15}

In 2015, the ReinHeart TAH GmbH was founded as a spinoff company of RWTH Aachen University, with the aim of bringing the product to the market. The company has been successfully able to integrate the driver electronics into the drive unit, reducing the number of system components. At the same time, the implantable pump unit was reduced in volume by about 20% because the intrathoracic space for implantation is limited.¹⁶ The resulting device (in the following called TAH 2.0) is based on the same driving technology, but the downsizing changes the nominal operating point of the pump unit.

The hydraulic characterization of the device can be described by the preload and afterload dependency of the resulting flow. In general, a TAH needs to ensure a balance between left and right flow. Mainly caused by the bronchial shunt flow (BSF), the left side of the heart has to provide a higher blood flow than the right side.¹⁷ In a study by DeVries et al, the difference for a TAH patient is reported to be 0.8 L/min.¹⁸ Bhunia et al state that the value ranges from 0 to 1.4 L/min. In addition, they specify that the value increases over the time of the postoperative period for any individual patient.¹⁹ The flow balance of the SynCardia TAH is supported by the passive partial filling of the pump chambers.²⁰ The Carmat TAH uses pressure sensors and independent electro-hydraulic pumps.^{21,22} Kung et al state that a BSF setting between 0.2 and 0.7 L/min satisfies the physiologic needs for the application of an electro-hydraulic TAH.²³ In the in vitro study characterizing the MagScrew TAH, a BSF is considered in the physiological test scenario with a value of 5% of the left flow.²⁴ The regulation of the BSF consists

of a complex system depending on different factors, such as oxygen concentration.^{25,26} The invasive measuring method challenges to specify the BSF in an awake patient, which explains the wide range of values for the BSF.²⁶

It is necessary that the TAH 2.0 ensures a positive flow difference (left flow exceeds right flow) over a wide range of preloads, which interferes with the passive filling feature of the device. The controllability shall allow an active adaption of the flow balance.

The objective of this study is to identify the preload and afterload sensitivity of the TAH 2.0. Furthermore, the controllability under different scenarios will be considered to evaluate possible limitations of the flow balance. To address this objective, a hydrodynamic study is carried out using an active mock circulation loop (MCL).

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | The ReinHeart TAH

The ReinHeart TAH 2.0 includes a fully implantable pump unit, consisting of a linear actuator with a left and right pump chamber. As shown in Figure 1, the pump unit (1) is connected to the extracorporeal Control and Monitoring Unit (3) via the driveline (2). A sinusoidal movement allows blood to be ejected alternately from the left and right pump chamber. Polyurethane membranes are used to separate the pump chambers from the linear actuator. The blood flow through the pump chambers is directed by bileaflet prosthetic heart valves, two in each chamber. For the left inlet, the ONXA-23 (CryoLife Inc., Kennesaw, USA) is used, whereas for the other three positions the ONXA-19 is used.

The periodic motion of the linear actuator pushes the diaphragm into the pump chamber during systole to eject the

FIGURE 1 The ReinHeart TAH 2.0 system; pump unit (1) connected via driveline (2) to the external power supply (3); the volume compensator (4) is connected via tubing to the pump unit [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

blood. In the subsequent diastole, the actuator separates from the membrane, and the pump chamber is filled passively. To enable the passive filling, the two membranes of the pump chambers are pneumatically decoupled by using a volume compensator (4).²⁷

Because the left and right sides cannot be controlled independently from each other, concepts of providing a flow balance regulation needed to be developed. In a previous study, several different concepts of right-left flow balance regulation have been investigated.²⁶ It was shown that a combination of a reduced right stroke volume together with an active control of the diastole duration resulted in an adequate flow balance.²⁸ Compared with the left pump chamber, with an effective stroke volume of 45 mL, the stroke volume of the right pump chamber was reduced by design. The reduction of the effective right stroke volume by 10% was verified in a static measurement prior to the study.

The duration of the right diastole (RD) can be varied within a range of 30% to 60% with respect to a complete cycle. Due to the mechanical coupling of both sides, an RD of 60% would result in a left diastole (LD) of 40%. The lower limit for the heart rate (HR) was determined from an expert survey on the minimum cardiac demand of a patient with typical chronic heart failure. This value was specified with an amount of 3.5 L/min, which is exceeded above an HR of 100 min⁻¹. The maximum value of 180 min⁻¹ was chosen, because of a possible increased risk of cavitation and a raised level of hemolysis caused by the heart valves.

In comparison with the native heart, the nominal HR of the TAH is slightly higher with a typical value of 140 min⁻¹, mainly caused by the smaller stroke volume of the device. The nominal HR was defined as the value of HR to achieve a left flow of 5 L/min.

Both parameters, HR and RD directly influence the filling time in the corresponding pump chamber and thus the degree of filling. An incomplete filling of the pump chamber results in a reduced flow output of the chamber. Hence, both parameters have a direct impact on the flow balance of the TAH. In dependence of HR, the left and right diastolic duration in seconds can be calculated as follows:

$$T_{\text{Dias}, L} = \text{LD} \times \frac{60 \text{ s}}{\text{HR}} \quad (1)$$

$$T_{\text{Dias}, R} = \text{RD} \times \frac{60 \text{ s}}{\text{HR}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{LD} = 100\% - \text{RD} \quad (3)$$

With higher HR, the diastolic duration of both sides becomes shorter. When RD is increased, the RD duration $T_{\text{Dias}, R}$ is prolonged, whereas the LD duration $T_{\text{Dias}, L}$ is shortened.

In this study, all the depicted combinations of HR and RD are tested under various pressure conditions to verify the functioning of the flow-balance regulation over a variety of operation points.

2.2 | Mock circulation loop

The experimental study was performed using an active MCL with lumped elements simulating the systemic and pulmonary arterial compliance (SAC, PAC), the systemic and pulmonary vascular resistance (SVR, PVR), and the systemic and pulmonary venous compliance (SVC, PVC).²⁹ The schematic of the hydraulic simulator is shown in Figure 2. Silicone atria connect the venous circulation to the TAH, outflow grafts provide a connection to the arterial compliances.

In this study, both atria are connected to each other by the technical interatrial shunt (TIAS), enabling independent testing of the left and right output of the TAH. The use of the TIAS is not intended to simulate neither an atrial septum defect nor a patent foramen ovale, but to compensate for a volume shift between the pulmonary and systemic circulation, as a result of a possible flow imbalance. With a direct connection between the left and right atrium, both pressures can be adjusted by a volume shift via the venous reservoir (VRS). The VRS is an electrically adjustable volume tank hydraulically connected to the venous side of the systemic and pulmonary circulation. By changing the VRS volume, the mean circulatory filling pressure can actively be changed to adjust the atrial pressure (AP).

An aqueous glycerol solution (40 mass-% glycerol) with a target viscosity of 3.6 mPas at room temperature was used to reproduce the viscosity of blood with a normal hematocrit for the relevant shear force range.³⁰ Over the entire measurement duration of 1 week, a viscosity with a value range of 3.58 ± 0.029 mPas was measured.

The pleural cavity was simulated using a pleura simulator (PLS). A negative gauge pressure of -4 mm Hg was created by a water column of 5.5 cm in a sealed container simulating the intra-pleural pressure conditions. The VC was placed inside this container. In the Online Supporting Information, the complete test setup of the MCL and the TAH is shown in Figure A. In addition, the schematic drawing of the PLS is illustrated in Figure B.

Pressures at the inlets and outlets of the TAH were measured by pressure transducers (DPT-9009; Codan, Lensahn, Germany) in combination with an analog amplifier (GSV-1A8, ME-Messsysteme, Henningsdorf, Germany). Left and right flow (also referred to as systemic and pulmonary flow) were measured with calibrated ultrasonic flow probe ME20PXL in combination with a TS410 tubing flow module (Transonic Systems Inc. USA). All analog pressure and flow signals were sampled with 1 kHz using a real-time data acquisition system (MicroLabBox, ds1202, dSPACE, Paderborn, Germany).

FIGURE 2 Mock circulation loop with six active elements (orange): systemic and pulmonary arterial compliance (SAC, PAC), pulmonary and systemic vascular resistance (PVR, SVR), venous reservoir (VRS) and technical interatrial shunt (TIAS); passive elements (white): pulmonary and aortic graft (PG, AG), left and right atria (LA, RA) and pulmonary and systemic venous compliance (PVC, SVC); volume compensator (VC) placed in the pleura simulator (PLS); measurement points (blue): measurement of aortic pressure (AoP), pulmonary artery pressure (PAP), left and right atrial pressure (LAP, RAP), systemic and pulmonary flow (Q_s , Q_p) [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

Active element	Unit	Parameter value
SVR (MAP control)	mm Hg	60, 80, 100, 120, 140
PVR (PAP control)	mm Hg	15, 20, 25, 30, 40
SAC	mL/mm Hg	1
PAC	mL/mm Hg	3
SVC	mL/mm Hg	107
PVC	mL/mm Hg	8
VRS (AP control)	mm Hg	4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20
TIAS	–	Open
HR	minute ⁻¹	100, 110, 120, 130, 140, 150, 160, 170, 180
RD	%	30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60

TABLE 1 Parameter variation of elements of the mock circulation loop and the total artificial heart; mean aortic pressure (MAP) was used to control systemic vascular resistance (SVR)

Notes: Pulmonary artery pressure (PAP) was used to control pulmonary vascular resistance (PVR). Atrial pressure (AP) was alternated by venous reservoir (VRS) up to a pressure of 20 mm Hg, representing elevated central venous pressure. Values for SVR and PVR cover the range between normotensive and severe hypertension.^{31,32} Throughout the study systemic arterial compliance (SAC), pulmonary arterial compliance (PAC), systemic venous compliance (SVC) and pulmonary venous compliance (PVC) were kept constant to their values for heart failure described by Cuenca et al.²⁹

2.3 | Parameter variation and experimental design

For the in vitro characterization of the TAH, the following parameter variations are used, as specified in Table 1. Values for HR and RD cover the complete intended operating limits. SAC, PAC, SVC, and PVC were kept constant throughout the study to the defined values representing heart failure.²⁹

Values for SVR and PVR cover the range between a physiological value and severe hypertension for mean aortic pressure (MAP) and mean pulmonary artery pressure (PAP), respectively.^{31,32}

By using a customized automation program, all parameter variations were sent to the MCL, according to the predefined test sequences. All active elements (SAC, PAC, SVR, PVR, and VRS) of the MCL as well as the settings of the TAH (HR, RD,

RD) were set automatically. Thus, high accuracy and user-independent repeatability can be ensured as only the user monitors the test sequence.

Once a steady-state was reached a measurement of 20s was triggered.

This in vitro study covers three types of characterization:

2.3.1 | Preload sensitivity

The MCL was filled with 5.4 L of the test fluid. To simulate different levels of preload of the left and right pump chamber, the volume of the VRS was varied to cover an AP range between 4 and 20 mm Hg. The afterload was kept constant to a mean AoP of 100 mm Hg and a mean PAP of 25 mm Hg by an automatic control loop tuning the SVR and PVR. The TAH was operated with an RD of 45%; HR was varied between 100 and 180 min⁻¹.

2.3.2 | Afterload sensitivity

Simulating different levels of afterload in the systemic and pulmonary circulation, SVR and PVR were used in a closed-loop control to track the reference MAP and mean PAP according to Table 1. Left and right APs were kept constant to a value of 10 mm Hg, and the RD was set to 45%.

2.3.3 | Controllability of flow balance

Four scenarios (high and low afterload in combination with high and low preload) are examined to evaluate the capability of the flow balance adjustment. For the combinations of low and high pre- and afterload, the influence of HR and RD are investigated. Low and high preload was defined as an AP of 6 mm Hg and 16 mm Hg, respectively. Afterload was defined as the combination of MAP/PAP, 80/20 mm Hg for low afterload and 140/40 mm Hg for high afterload scenario. The difference between left and right flow is calculated. As reported in the two studies with patients with TAH, the difference between left and right flow can vary from 0 to 1.4 L/min.^{18,19} In accordance with the previous investigation on different flow balance concepts, the interval from 0 to 1.5 L/min is selected as the target range to assess the controllability of the flow balance.²⁸ For each scenario, it is verified whether the target area is fully met and how many combinations of HR and RD result in the performance within the targeted area.

Data analysis was carried out using MATLAB 2019b (The MathWorks, USA). Mean values for pressures and flows were calculated and are used in the following to characterize the hydrodynamic behavior.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Preload sensitivity

Figure 3 illustrates the preload sensitivity of the left and right pump chamber as a function of AP and HR. Two sections can be identified for the preload sensitivity of the left side. Between approx. 4 and 10 mm Hg the left flow increases with rising pressure. The preload sensitivity can be described as the slope of the graphs. A mean preload sensitivity of 0.1977 ± 0.185 L/min/mm Hg (mean \pm SD) can be calculated, ranging from 0.0266 (HR = 100 min⁻¹) to 0.5913 L/min/mm Hg (HR = 180 min⁻¹) for an AP between 4 and 10 mm Hg. Above an AP of about 10 mm Hg, the flow remains constant and is only depending on the value of HR. The preload sensitivity decreases to a mean value of 0.0116 ± 0.0210 L/min/mm Hg.

For the nominal HR of 140 min⁻¹ the left flow increases, starting at 4.2 L/min at the lowest inlet pressure, to a range between 5.0 and 5.3 L/min above an LAP of 8 mm Hg.

A positive correlation between right AP and right flow can be observed over the complete range. The mean preload sensitivity of the right side is 0.1854 ± 0.054 L/min/mm Hg. For a low inlet pressure of 3.4 mm Hg, the maximum flow amounts up to 4.3 L/min with an HR of 180 min⁻¹. The flow continues to increase up to a value of 7.3 L/min for the maximum HR.

At the nominal HR of 140 min⁻¹, the right flow increases, starting at 3.8 L/min, to a maximum value of 5.7 L/min at 15 mm Hg.

3.2 | Afterload sensitivity

Figure 4 illustrates the average left and right flow over the range of increasing HR and afterload (MAP and PAP, respectively).

As MAP is rising, a decrease of left flow can be observed. Over the full range of MAP and HR, the mean afterload sensitivity is -0.0066 ± 0.004 L/min/mm Hg. For HR between 100 and 140 min⁻¹, the increase in afterload leads to a constant reduction in flow. At an HR of 150 min⁻¹ or higher, the flow starts to increase again with increasing afterload. At an HR of 180 min⁻¹, the left flow fluctuates but shows no clear dependence on the afterload.

Independent of HR, right flow mostly decreases with rising afterload over the pressure range of 15 to 40 mm Hg, with an afterload sensitivity of -0.0218 ± 0.007 L/min/mm Hg. For almost all values of HR the flow remains constant for a PAP between 20 and 30 mm Hg, before it drops again toward higher afterload.

3.3 | Controllability of the TAH

For the four scenarios of low and high preload in combination with low and high afterload, the maximum achievable

FIGURE 3 Left and right flow depending on the inlet pressure of the pump; mean aortic pressure was kept at 100 mm Hg, mean pulmonary artery pressure at 25 mm Hg, right diastole was set to 45%, heart rate was alternated from 100 to 180 min⁻¹ [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

FIGURE 4 Left and right flow in response to afterload pressure and heart rate; left and right atrial pressures were kept constant at 10 mm Hg [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

flow difference is shown in Figure 5. The areas are color-coded when the value is located within the target range of 0-1.5 L/min (or even higher).

For low preload and afterload (A), the target range extends almost completely over the entire test range of HR and RD. A maximum difference of even more than 2 L/min can be observed in the upper left triangle (HR: 150-180 min⁻¹, RD 30%-40%). When afterload is increased (B), the target range is reduced, but it is still completely covered. The maximum difference results for an HR of 170 min⁻¹ and RD of 45%. In the matrix for low afterload and high preload (C), it can be seen that the target range is only reached for 9 of a total of 63 combinations. A maximum difference of 1.2 L/min is achieved with an HR of 180 min⁻¹ and an RD of 30%. When afterload is increased again (D), the target range is covered by 23 of 63 combinations. However, the maximum adjustable difference in this scenario amounts only to 0.7 L/min.

4 | DISCUSSIONS

This study has characterized the hydrodynamic behavior of the downsized TAH over a wide range of operating points. In addition to the two parameters HR and RD, correlations between the flow and the corresponding preload and afterload of the pump chamber could be identified.

4.1 | Preload and afterload sensitivity

Both pump chambers show different dependencies on the preload. Although the left flow was only dependent on the inlet pressure up to a value of about 10 mm Hg, a positive correlation between flow and inlet pressure could be shown for the right pump chamber for the whole tested pressure range. The different behavior of the two pump chambers might result from different designs: A 10% lower stroke volume was implemented

FIGURE 5 Flow difference (in L/min) between left and right flow; low preload is defined as 6 mm Hg, high preload as 16 mm Hg; low afterload: mean aortic pressure (MAP) 80 mm Hg, pulmonary artery pressure (PAP) 20 mm Hg; high afterload: MAP 140 mm Hg, PAP 40 mm Hg; areas are color-coded when value is within target range of 0-1.5 L/min (or higher) [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

TABLE 2 Overview of left preload sensitivity of different pulsatile total artificial heart (TAH) systems and the human ventricle, modified from³⁵

Device	Pump type	Preload sensitivity (in L/min/mm Hg)
ReinHeart TAH 2.0	Free filling	0.1977 ± 0.185
Abiocor TAH	Free filling	0.400
MagScrew TAH	Free filling	0.640
Penn State/3M TAH	Free filling	1.000
Utah-100 (Jarvik)	Active suction	1.400
Native ventricle	Left ventricle	0.241 ± 0.040

Notes: Abiocor (Abiomed, Danvers, MA, USA), Cleveland Clinic MagScrew, Utah-100 the predecessor of the SynCardia TAH (SynCardia, Tucson, AZ, USA).

on the right side compared with the left side to provide an initial offset for the adjustment of flow balance. A second difference in the design of both pump chambers is the size of the inlet valve. Although a 23-mm valve is used in the mitral position (left side), a 19-mm valve is mounted at the right inlet. Hartrumpf et al have shown that bi-leaflet valves with smaller diameters create higher mean pressure gradients. In the same study, it was stated that the regurgitation volume increase with the diameter of the heart valve.³³ In addition, Bottio et al have demonstrated, on the one hand, that the leakage volume of a 19-mm heart valve is independent of the cardiac output. However, the closing volume decreases with higher values of cardiac output.³⁴ These effects appear to oppose, but they negatively affect the stroke volume and thus the flow.

Table 2 provides an overview of the preload sensitivity of pulsatile TAH systems and the human left ventricle under resting conditions. In comparison with other pulsatile TAH systems, the preload sensitivity of the ReinHeart TAH 2.0 appears to be lower. Especially, the Utah-100, the predecessor of the SynCardia TAH, shows a high preload sensitivity, mostly supported by the active filling of the ventricle. Compared with the human left ventricle, the downsized TAH has a preload sensitivity of the same magnitude.

As presented by Crosby et al the SynCardia TAH shows no sensitivity to a raised afterload between 85 and 135 mm Hg aortic pressure because it is driven by a pneumatic driver with a driving pressure of 180 mm Hg.³⁵ In addition, the MagScrew TAH has an approximate afterload insensitive left pump, while a small decrease in flow of the right pump was observed with increasing afterload.²⁴ For the human left ventricle, an afterload sensitivity of -0.041 ± 0.020 L/min/mm Hg can be calculated.³⁶ The left afterload sensitivity of the downsized TAH 2.0 has a value of -0.006 ± 0.004 L/min/mm Hg, which is less sensitive than the human left ventricle.

Comparing the left and right side, although the mean preload sensitivity is similar, with a value of 0.1997 to 0.1854 L/min/mm Hg, the left pump chamber has a higher dependence

on HR in the range between 4 and 10 mm Hg preload. The right afterload sensitivity is 3 to 4 times higher than the left afterload sensitivity.

The contrasting sensitivities of both pump chambers to the preload support the adjustment of the flow balance. Whereas the right flow depends on the inlet pressure over the entire pressure range, the left flow reaches the maximum value from 10 mm Hg at the latest (for slower HR at even lower values). This preload sensitivity shows an advantageous behavior because a complete filling of the left pump chamber enables a maximum left flow. With the variation of RD, the right filling can be reduced to achieve a positive flow difference. This condition also implies a physiological limit for the flow balance of the TAH. Due to the positive correlation between RAP and right flow, at relatively high values of RAP, the right flow could exceed the left flow. The flow difference is analyzed in more detail in the following section.

At an HR of 150 min^{-1} or higher, an increase in flow could be measured at a value of 140 mm Hg for the AoP although an overall negative correlation between flow and afterload could be identified. At even higher values of HR, the increase in flow already starts at lower values for AoP. In these marginal areas, the high acceleration of the TAH's actuator combined with the required force to eject the fluid causes the actuator to no longer completely follow the target position of the trajectory. Overshoot in the end positions leads to increased ejection and thus higher flow.

The right side of the TAH shows an overall negative correlation between flow and afterload. Different mutual effects could explain the graph progression for PAP between 20 and 30 mm Hg. The leakage volume of the inlet and outlet valves as well as the closing volume may not only be pressure-sensitive but also depending on fluid velocity, directly influenced by HR.³⁴ The passive characteristic of the pump chambers' membrane shows a highly nonlinear pressure-volume dependency, which may also explain the measured afterload sensitivity.³⁷ In further studies, these effects shall be investigated.

4.2 | Controllability of the flow

In the four defined scenarios, the previously isolated aspects of preload and afterload sensitivity are considered in combination. In addition to the pressure conditions, the flow balance can be adjusted by a suitable choice of HR and RD.

Scenario A, with low preload and low afterload, defines the initial situation for controllability of the flow balance. The difference between left and right flow is always positive for values of RD smaller than 60% in this scenario. When the left and right diastolic times are identical (RD equal to 50%), the difference of left and right pump chambers' size can be observed. Reducing the right pump chamber's stroke volume in this case results in a positive

difference in stroke volume with an average of 3.2 mL over the entire range of HR.

Increasing the preload or afterload, the range of combination to set a positive flow difference declines. This range is located in the upper left corner, meaning that either HR must be raised or RD must be shortened, or the combination of both.

In both scenarios C and D, the preload is increased, exposing the different characteristics of the left and right pump chambers. Due to the positive correlation between inlet pressure and right flow, the latter exceeds the value of left flow for most of the combinations of HR and RD. The high right inlet pressure requires that an RD of less than 35% has to be selected to achieve a positive flow difference of more than 0.5 L/min.

An adjustment of HR also influences the absolute value of the left and right flow. This leads to an increase in pressure when resistance remains constant. The physiological adaptation of the cardiovascular system to the changed pressure and flow values are disregarded in this *in vitro* study. It is, therefore, necessary to also verify the controllability of the flow balance in *in vivo* trials.

Under normotensive conditions, the mean LAP exceeds the value of RAP. This fact additionally supports the flow balance due to the different preload sensitivities.

4.3 | The effect of downsizing

The downsizing of the TAH enabled a volume reduction of the intrathoracic pump unit of about 20%. By downsizing the TAH, we intend to make this potential therapy available to a larger cohort of patients as the thoracic space is limited.¹⁶

Figure 6 shows the maximum left flow over the full range of HR under physiological test conditions for the former TAH system, described by Pelletier et al, and the TAH 2.0.¹³ The linear relationship describes the effective stroke volume of both systems. By downsizing the pump unit, the effective stroke volume has been reduced from 48 mL to approx. 36.3 mL. At a maximum HR of 180 min⁻¹, a left flow of 6.8 L/min can be achieved.

To maintain a pump flow of 5 L/min, the nominal HR was increased from 110 to 140 min⁻¹. This shift of the design operating point to a higher velocity has an influence on the mechanical properties and the hydraulic characteristic.

In addition to the reevaluation of the hydraulic characteristic, we are currently investigating the effect of downsizing on the durability and the hemolysis of the TAH.³⁸ Virtual and anatomical fitting studies are carried out to determine a possible patient cohort and to validate the effect of the downsizing. The device is being tested in chronic animal trials to validate the *in vitro* study and the device's performance.

4.4 | Limitations

By using the TIAS, the systemic and pulmonary circulations were operated in a decoupled configuration with connected atria. In this setup, the left and right sides of the TAH could be tested separately from each other. Under physiological conditions, a flow imbalance also leads to an interaction with the systemic and pulmonary circulation, resulting in changing preload conditions. These effects will be investigated in further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies.

FIGURE 6 Comparison of left flow depending on heart rate of the former ReinHeart TAH and the ReinHeart TAH 2.0, adapted from¹³ [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

APs below 4 mm Hg could not be established in the MCL due to air being drawn into the circulation through the open vessel, used to simulate the pulmonary venous compliance. Identifying the behavior of the device even for low AP may be of interest to determine the minimal inlet pressure for an adequate pump flow.

In a still-running series of animal trials, we observed the impact of positive pressure ventilation and movement of the diaphragm on the filling of the atria. Furthermore, the time-varying intrathoracic pressure influences the filling of the atria and, therefore, the preload of the TAH.³⁹ These effects are not modeled in this study but may interfere with the filling of the TAH. The interactions that also result from the anatomical fit can only be studied in chronic animal experiments.

5 | CONCLUSION

This in vitro study identifies the hydrodynamic characteristics in terms of preload and afterload dependencies of the downsized TAH 2.0. The controllability of the device was successfully evaluated in four scenarios, revealing that a positive flow balance (higher left than right flow) can be achieved over the full range of MAP between 60 and 140 mm Hg. At high right inlet pressure, a flow difference of up to 0.7 L/min could be obtained.

The reduced right stroke volume in combination with a larger left inlet valve supports the setting of an adequate left-right flow balance. The preload sensitivity of the left pump chamber supports reaching the maximum flow at an inlet pressure of 8–10 mm Hg. With the active adjustment of RD, the right flow can be additionally decreased to achieve a positive flow difference.

Under physiological conditions, the linear relationship between flow and HR was confirmed. The downsizing of the TAH resulted in a reduction of stroke volume, but the designed flow can be achieved: A flow of 6.8 L/min at an HR of 180 min⁻¹ over the full range of aortic pressure. An increase in nominal HR from 110 to 140 min⁻¹ allows maintaining a left flow of 5 L/min.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Heiko De Ben, Elena Cuenca, and Thomas Finocchiaro are employees at ReinHeart TAH GmbH. Apart from that, all authors declare no conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Writing article, study design and conception, data acquisition, analysis and interpretation of data: Hildebrand

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional Supporting Information may be found online in the Supporting Information section.

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